

Cooperative Students: Navigating Unsupervised Domain Adaptation in Nighttime Object Detection

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Abstract—Unsupervised Domain Adaptation (UDA) has shown significant advancements in object detection under well-lit conditions; however, its performance degrades notably in low-visibility scenarios, especially at night, posing challenges not only for its adaptability in low signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) conditions but also for the reliability and efficiency of automated vehicles. To address this problem, we propose a Cooperative Students (CoS) framework that innovatively employs global-local transformations (GLT) and a proxy-based target consistency (PTC) mechanism to capture the spatial consistency in day- and nighttime scenarios effectively, and thus bridge the significant domain shift across contexts. Building upon this, we further devise an adaptive IoU-informed thresholding (AIT) module to gradually avoid overlooking potential true positives and enrich the latent information in the target domain. Comprehensive experiments show that CoS essentially enhanced UDA performance in low-visibility conditions and surpasses current state-of-the-art techniques, achieving an increase in mAP of 3.0%, 1.9%, and 2.5% on BDD100K, SHIFT, and ACDC datasets, respectively. Code is available at this [GitHub repository](#).

Index Terms—Object Detection, Mutual Learning, UDA

I. INTRODUCTION

Object detection has made significant advancements with the advent of deep learning techniques [1]. While available approaches perform exceptionally well under standard lighting conditions, they often falter in nighttime or low-light scenarios. The differences in illumination, shadows, and contrasts between daytime and nighttime contexts pose significant challenges for models serving for autonomous driving, particularly in environments such as rural areas or highways where artificial lighting is sparse. Previous studies [2], [3] primarily focused on supervised learning with synthetic data or semi-supervised domain adaptation, where labeled data from the target domain is a prerequisite.

However, obtaining labeled data for every possible domain is resource-intensive and often impractical. This has led to the emergence of unsupervised domain adaptation (UDA) as a potential solution. The fundamental premise of UDA in day-to-

Fig. 1: Differences between CoS and other UDA methods. (a) Pseudo-labels (PLs) and uncertain proposals in traditional solutions. (b) and (c) PLs proposed by CoS. (d) Performance comparisons on BDD100K [4] with varying data usage. More examples are shown in the supplement. (The image was enhanced for better visibility.)

night scenarios is to utilize models trained on daytime images and adapt them to nighttime conditions without the need for human- or model-driven annotations in the target domain. In this paradigm, the target domain benefits from latent information learned by the detector trained on the source domain. Yet, this is not without its challenges: ① A key observation in UDA for object detection is the variance in object appearances and backgrounds across domains [5]. While some methods [6], [7] focus on aligning feature distributions between the source and target domains, others [8], [9] emphasize pseudo-labeling techniques to iteratively guide the model learning on the target domain. ② Due to the large domain gap, pseudo-labels

(PLs) produced by the source domain detector for the target (nighttime) domain often lack the requisite accuracy, struggling to identify and localize objects with desired qualities. Current UDA methods [10], [11] produced PLs focus predominantly on the confidence derived from the classification branch, often neglecting potential localization information or inherent uncertainty in challenging yet prone to be overlooked objects, as demonstrated in Figure 1 (a). ③ Relying solely on a static threshold focusing on classification confidence for PLs filtering often overlooks the fact that the model’s prediction confidence varies across categories and iterations, leading to inconsistent targets and adversely impacting the performance [12], [13]. Thus, the adaptive generation of high-quality PLs and the avoidance of overlooking potential true positives (TPs) are crucial for robust adaptation from daytime to nighttime contexts.

In this work, we propose **Cooperative Students (CoS)**, a novel mutual-learning-based UDA framework for object detection from daytime- to nighttime- contexts, leveraging the teacher-student architecture [14]. To address the challenge ①, we introduce a parameter-free global-local transformation (GLT) module to enhance daytime images with shared prior knowledge like lighting and contrast information in nighttime scenarios, thus guiding the detector to capture semantically consistent object features across domains. Against the challenge ②, we incorporate a proxy-based target consistency (PTC) module, leveraging mutual consistency in both classification and localization branches between teacher- and proxy-student-network, aiming to iteratively refine the learned latent information and pseudo-label qualities used to guide the student network advancing in nighttime images, as depicted in Figure 1 (b) and (c). Additionally, building upon PTC, we develop an adaptive IoU-informed thresholding (AIT) strategy to expand the potential searching space for consistent positive samples, addressing the challenge ③. Through these, we aim to establish a more coherent domain adaptation, resulting in enhanced performance in UDA for nighttime object detection. Our contributions are summarized as follows:

- We develop a GLT module that enhances daytime images utilizing prior knowledge from nighttime scenarios, serving as a basic adaptation unit aiming at reducing the domain gap without losing the semantic relevance.
- We introduce a PTC module that incorporates classification and localization information to capture overlooked consistent targets, iteratively refining the learning on nighttime images and avoiding the neglect of valuable predictions.
- Based on PTC, we further adopt an AIT strategy to widen the potential searching space of true positives.
- Extensive experiments verify that CoS outperforms existing unsupervised methods in day-to-night adaptation under various proportions of used data, as shown in Figure 1 (d).

II. RELATED WORK

Unsupervised Domain Adaptation leverages labeled data from the source domain to train models, adapting them to

the target domain and achieving better performance without accessing its annotations. Traditional approaches [6], [7], [15] aim to minimize domain discrepancies through feature alignment. Conversely, [16], [17] employs a domain discriminator for mining domain-agnostic features. Others [18]–[20], either employing synthetic data or adversarial examples to reduce the domain gap, are effective in UDA. However, these solutions are resource-intensive. Different from them, we develop a parameter-free GLT module, enhancing images in the source domain by leveraging prior knowledge from the target domain.

UDA in Nighttime Contexts has gained significant traction in dealing with tasks in low-visibility scenarios with limited or without annotations, whereby most research focuses on semantic segmentation [21], [22] and object tracking [23]. DANNet [22] introduces a DA network tailored for nighttime semantic segmentation without needing labeled nighttime data. In aerial tracking, UDAT [23] employs a transformer-based bridging layer as a feature discriminator between domains, training the daytime model adversarially for nighttime adaptation. For object detection, AugGAN [24] incorporates synthetic datasets to bridge the day-night disparity. 2PCNet [11] introduces a two-phase consistency to mitigate domain shift. While these UDA solutions are effective, they primarily rely on classification confidence in producing PLs. In contrast, our approach uniquely emphasizes mutual consistency, combining classification and localization to mine consistent targets with semantic relevance across contexts, thus reducing the divergence between domains.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Overview and Problem Definition

UDA in nighttime object detection poses greater challenges than conventional UDA (under well-fit conditions) due to the sharp illumination shifts, divergent feature quality, and low SNR [24]. Different from prior approaches [11], [17], CoS eases these challenges by capturing semantic relevance across domains and localization consistency of potential true positives (TPs) using a mutual-learning-based teacher-student network (TSN). Define $\mathcal{D}_s = \{\mathcal{I}_s^{N_s}, \mathcal{B}_s^M, \mathcal{C}_s^M\}$ as N_s samples from the source domain, with $\mathcal{B}_s^M \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times 4}$ as bounding boxes, and \mathcal{C}_s^M as class labels of M box-level annotations. Conversely, the target domain, characterized by nighttime imagery, is denoted as $\mathcal{D}_t = \{\mathcal{I}_t^{N_t}\}$. To ensure the quality of pseudo-labels (PLs) in the early stage UDA, images from the source domain are utilized for the initial training of the student network. The supervised loss \mathcal{L}_{sup} comprises the losses from the RPN network and RoI head as:

$$\min_{\Theta_s} \sum_i^{N_s} [\mathcal{L}_{rpn}(f_s(\mathcal{I}_{sa}^i), \mathcal{B}_s^i) + \mathcal{L}_{roi}(f_s(\mathcal{I}_{sa}^i, \mathcal{B}_s^i, \mathcal{I}_{sa}^i))], \quad (1)$$

where $f_s(\cdot; \Theta_s)$ is the student detector, and \mathcal{I}_{sa} denotes images enhanced by the GLT module, as detailed in Section III-B. Following the supervised warm-up training, we initialize the teacher network using parameters from the student network. In the subsequent UDA phase, the teacher model

Fig. 2: Network Architecture of the proposed CoS: The key components include the Global-Local Transformation module, serving to reduce the domain gap while maintaining semantic relevance between source and target through prior knowledge from the target domain; Proxy-based target consistency module works to capture overlooked consistent targets; and adaptive IoU-informed thresholding strategy expands the searching space for potential true positives. During domain adaptation, the corresponding source domain data will be used for initial training and the target domain data will be used as inputs during the unsupervised learning stage. The refined label will be used to supervise the second student network (the bottom one). Both subnetworks have the same structure that has components: RoI and detection head with shared RPN and feature extractor. The unsupervised losses, $\mathcal{L}_{cls}^{unsup}$ and $\mathcal{L}_{loc}^{unsup}$ are considered between the bottom student network and the consistent PLs $\hat{\mathcal{P}}_t^{T_p}$ produced by teacher and proxy student networks.

produces PLs for \mathcal{D}_t , guiding the learning of the student network. As training advances, the quality of PLs will be progressively enhanced. However, a prevalent issue arises, as uncertain proposals depicted in green boxes in Figure 1 (a), potential targets are intentionally excluded due to their classified confidences not reaching a predefined rigid threshold τ_{se}^{cls} . To address this, we propose a proxy student network to ensure localization consistency for those overlooked potential TPs. Specifically, when identical category proposals emerge from both networks for a specific potential object, even if their confidences fall below the threshold τ_{se}^{cls} , target consistency can be achieved based on the precision of mutual localizations, as the proposals with red \star depicted in Figure 1 (a), (b). Those matched proposals are then incorporated as extra candidates for PLs. Subsequently, the extended PLs $\hat{\mathcal{P}}_t^{T_p}(\hat{\mathcal{B}}_t^{T_p}, \hat{\mathcal{C}}_t^{T_p})$, collaboratively validated by the teacher and proxy-student networks, are employed to guide the learning of the student network (bottom part of Figure 2). They serve to minimize the unsupervised loss in the target domain:

$$\min_{\Theta_s} \sum_i^{N_t} \left[\mathcal{L}_{cls}(f_s(\mathcal{I}_t^i), \hat{\mathcal{C}}_t^{T_p i}) + \mathcal{L}_{reg}(f_s(\mathcal{I}_t^i), \hat{\mathcal{B}}_t^{T_p i}) \right], \quad (2)$$

Additionally, we utilize the Exponential Moving Average (EMA) [14] to transfer the knowledge learned by the student detector $f_s(\cdot; \Theta_t)$ back to the teacher detector $f_t(\cdot; \Theta_t)$, as defined in Equation 3:

$$\Theta_t = \alpha \cdot \Theta_{t-1} + (1 - \alpha) \cdot \Theta_s, \quad (3)$$

where Θ_t and Θ_s denote learnable parameters from the teacher and student network. Furthermore, to expand the searching space in the target domain and enhance detector performance as learning advances, we introduce an AIT module to adjust τ_{se}^{cls} dynamically, as detailed in Section III-D. This contrasts with prior works [10], [17] that require a static threshold to filter valuable outputs as PLs.

B. Global-Local Transformation

Given our objective of performing UDA from daytime to nighttime contexts, the disparity between these domains, particularly in aspects like luminance conditions and visibility, is substantial. UDAT [23] introduced a domain discriminator to mitigate the large domain gap between source and target. However, it increases model complexity and can lead to negative adaptation [25]. Drawing inspiration from [11], [26], we introduce a parameter-free method, named global-local-transformation (GLT), to transfer the prior knowledge from source to target. For global brightness transformation, we first calculate the channel-wise mean and variance, denoted as μ_c^n, σ_c^n for nighttime images, and μ_c^d, σ_c^d for the daytime image to be enhanced. Next, the luminance offset is defined as $\Delta\mu_c = \mu_c^n - \mu_c^d$ and the adaptive parameter is given by $v_c = \beta \cdot \Delta\mu_c$, where $\beta \sim \mathcal{U}(0.2, 0.8)$ simulates the nighttime luminance variability. Subsequently, we adjust the brightness channel-wise in the daytime image, as Equation 4 outlined:

$$\mathcal{I}_{sa}^c(x, y) = \mathcal{I}_s^c(x, y) \cdot \max(0.2, \min(v_c, 1.0)), \quad (4)$$

Fig. 3: t-SNE [27] visualization of nighttime object features on BDD100K [4].

Similarly, we conduct contrast and gamma correction to daytime images. Additionally, it is crucial to note that beyond the evident inter-domain gaps, substantial intra-domain discrepancies exist, including fluctuations in illumination and shadow presence on objects. Specifically, brightness inconsistencies can manifest across various regions of the same object captured at nighttime, influenced by factors like localized dim lighting or intense directional illumination. Hence, relying solely on global transformation can lead to regional feature discrepancies between nighttime and enhanced daytime images. To address this, we propose a box-level enhancement technique. In daytime images, we randomly set a pixel coordinate inside bounding boxes as the center point, around which a mask is positioned, either horizontally or vertically. Then, we reapply the brightness correction to this randomly mask area. The entire GLT pipeline is illustrated in the upper left block of Figure 2.

C. Proxy-based Target Consistency

In unsupervised learning using teacher-student-network (TSN) [14], pseudo-labels (PLs) are typically produced by the teacher based on classification confidences and a static secure threshold τ_{se}^{cls} [10], [17]. However, as learning progresses, reliance solely on confidence scores cannot guarantee the quality of PLs and model performance in identifying potential true positives (TPs) [12], as illustrated in Figure 1 (a). This implies that some TPs, accurately classified and localized by the teacher, may be inadvertently overlooked due to failing to meet the predefined τ_{se}^{cls} . To address this, we develop a novel proxy-based target consistency mechanism to automatically identify those consistent targets that were overlooked during learning. Specifically, a proxy student network (in the middle part of Figure 2), bridging the traditional teacher and student network, promotes the model to distinguish potential true positives in the overlooked predictions that fall below the secure threshold τ_{se}^{cls} , thus achieving target consistency among those uncertain predictions using auxiliary classification and localization information. As illustrated in Figure 2, our method comprises three main steps: Initially, during the UDA phase on nighttime images, we feed input data \mathcal{I}_t into the teacher network $f_t(\cdot; \Theta_t)$ to get their target outputs \mathcal{O}_t^T . Based on the \mathcal{O}_t^T and secure threshold τ_{se}^{cls} , the filtered initial PLs $\hat{\mathcal{P}}_t^T$ can

be obtained according to the Formula 5.

$$\hat{\mathcal{P}}_t^T(\hat{\mathcal{B}}_t^T, \hat{\mathcal{C}}_t^T) \leftarrow \mathcal{O}_t^T(\mathcal{B}_t^T, \mathcal{C}_t^T) \quad \text{where } \mathcal{C}_t^{T_i} \geq \tau_{se}^{cls}, \quad (5)$$

Similarly, the same nighttime input \mathcal{I}_t without annotations is fed into the proxy student network to obtain outputs \mathcal{O}_t^P . The initial PLs $\hat{\mathcal{P}}_t^T$ produced by the teacher network will guide the learning of the proxy student model, as $\mathcal{L}_t^P = \frac{1}{N_t} \sum_i \left[\mathcal{L}_{cls}(f_p(\mathcal{I}_t^i), \hat{\mathcal{C}}_t^{T_i}) + \mathcal{L}_{reg}(f_p(\mathcal{I}_t^i), \hat{\mathcal{B}}_t^{T_i}) \right]$. Next, outputs \mathcal{O}_t^T from the teacher and \mathcal{O}_t^P from the proxy student will be aggregated to produce second-stage PLs based on mutual classification and localization information, achieving target consistency. Specifically, the consistent targets will be mined between the uncertain (overlooked) predictions (from the teacher) and outputs \mathcal{O}_t^P (from the proxy student). The final mined consistent targets will be considered as pseudo-label candidates $\hat{\mathcal{P}}_t^P$ if two bounding boxes (one from teacher and another from proxy student) share identical category assignments and their localization consistency exceeds τ_{se}^{loc} (set at 0.8 in this work), as described in Formula 6.

$$\hat{\mathcal{P}}_t^P(\hat{\mathcal{B}}_t^P, \hat{\mathcal{C}}_t^P) = \mathcal{O}_t^T(\mathcal{B}_t^T, \mathcal{C}_t^T) \otimes \mathcal{O}_t^P(\mathcal{B}_t^P, \mathcal{C}_t^P),$$

$$\text{where } \operatorname{argmax}(\mathcal{C}_t^{T_i}) = \operatorname{argmax}(\mathcal{C}_t^{P_i}), \quad \mathcal{C}_t^{T_i} < \tau_{se}^{cls} \quad (6)$$

$$\text{and } \mathcal{F}_{loc}(\mathcal{B}_t^{T_i}, \mathcal{B}_t^{P_i}) \geq \tau_{se}^{loc}$$

Then, $\hat{\mathcal{P}}_t^T$ and $\hat{\mathcal{P}}_t^P$ are merged to form the final consistent pseudo-labels $\hat{\mathcal{P}}_t^{T_p}$, as defined in Formula 7,

$$\hat{\mathcal{P}}_t^{T_p}(\hat{\mathcal{B}}_t^r, \hat{\mathcal{C}}_t^r) = \hat{\mathcal{P}}_t^T(\hat{\mathcal{B}}_t^T, \hat{\mathcal{C}}_t^T) \oplus \hat{\mathcal{P}}_t^P(\hat{\mathcal{B}}_t^P, \hat{\mathcal{C}}_t^P), \quad (7)$$

guiding the learning of the student network, as depicted at the bottom of Figure 2. To guarantee the quality of the consistent PLs $\hat{\mathcal{P}}_t^{T_p}$ produced by teacher and proxy student networks, we use a warm-up phase: the PTC module will be introduced after 40% of iterations in the burn-up stage. During the warm-up phase, we follow the training setup in [10], solely the initial PLs $\hat{\mathcal{P}}_t^T$ generated by the teacher model are used to supervise the student network.

D. Adaptive IoU-Informed Thresholding

Prior studies [5], [30], [31] employed a static hyperparameter τ_{se}^{cls} to filter potential samples as PLs. However, this overlooks the variation in the model performance across iterations, leading to missing potential true positives and significantly impacting the overall learning progress. For instance, a high τ_{se}^{cls} can result in too many false negatives, while a low value may increase false positives, compromising model performance. To ease this, building upon the PTC module, we propose an Adaptive IoU-informed thresholding (AIT) strategy to adjust the τ_{se}^{cls} dynamically and capture potential TPs as learning advances. It adjusts the threshold by analyzing the consistent PLs derived from PTC and focuses on those samples that, even if they do not meet stringent classification thresholds, are significantly relevant in localization consistency, as illustrated in the upper right of Figure 2. Specifically, with AIT, the mean μ_t^P and variance σ_t^P are first calculated using the classification confidences above their $\operatorname{median}(\cdot)$ scores in matching boxes

Methods	Bicycle	Bus	Car	Rider	Truck	Motorcycle	Pedestrian	Traffic Light	Traffic Sign	AP
<i>Oracle:</i>										
Night-time	36.2	42.5	73.2	27.4	47.5	27.2	51.0	45.6	66.6	41.7
Day-&Night-time	42.7	51.6	75.5	<u>34.3</u>	56.1	36.3	<u>56.0</u>	51.8	<u>66.8</u>	<u>47.1</u>
<i>I2I based:</i>										
CycleGAN [28]	43.1	52.0	69.9	34.9	50.1	34.8	52.3	33.0	62.6	43.2
UNIT [29]	39.1	51.7	70.4	34.9	50.1	33.2	52.2	37.5	62.7	43.3
ForkGAN [19]	39.4	50.3	69.2	29.6	48.7	32.5	49.9	44.6	61.8	42.6
FourierDA [18]	38.2	49.0	69.4	26.5	44.2	30.2	46.2	43.2	61.5	41.8
<i>Enhance based:</i>										
DAF [5]	30.3	37.4	56.5	25.3	35.8	21.5	35.8	25.8	44.5	31.3
TDD [30]	25.9	35.6	68.4	20.7	33.3	16.5	43.1	43.1	59.5	34.6
SADAF [31]	33.0	35.1	67.7	24.3	38.6	33.0	49.7	<u>51.5</u>	61.4	38.4
Adaptive Teacher [17]	42.7	52.1	60.8	30.4	48.9	34.5	42.3	<u>29.1</u>	43.9	38.5
Unbiased Mean Teacher [10]	40.2	46.3	46.8	26.1	44.0	28.2	46.5	31.6	52.7	36.2
Two Phase Consistent Network [11]	<u>44.5</u>	<u>55.2</u>	73.1	30.8	53.8	<u>37.5</u>	54.4	49.4	65.2	46.4
Cooperative Students (Ours)	50.2	55.6	<u>73.9</u>	41.3	<u>54.7</u>	43.5	57.1	50.0	67.8	49.4

TABLE I: Performance comparison (in AP) of Cooperative Students with other approaches for day-to-night UDA. Results are shown for the supervised model (oracle), image-to-image translation (I2I-based), and image enhancement (enhancement-based) solutions on the BDD100K dataset. Bold represents the best performance, and underline indicates the second-best performance within each category.

Target Consistent Module	Global Trans.	Local Trans.	Threshold Decay	AP	AP ^L	AP ^M	AP ^S
				35.1	32.3	18.6	5.7
✓				41.3	38.4	23.3	7.9
✓		✓		44.0	39.6	19.3	8.4
✓	✓			47.9	42.2	26.8	9.2
✓	✓	✓		48.4	44.8	27.2	9.6
✓	✓	✓	✓	49.4	45.9	27.9	10.2

TABLE II: Ablation study on BDD100K [4].

between the teacher and proxy student network. Then, an auxiliary threshold update step is introduced: $\tau_{stp}^{cls} = \mu_t^P - 2 \times \sigma_t^P$. Next, The deviation for threshold adjustment is derived as: $\tau_{dev}^{cls} = \gamma(\tau_{stp}^{cls} - \tau_{se}^{cls})$. Here, γ is an adjustable parameter set by default at 0.05. The updated threshold, defined as $\tau_{upd}^{cls} = \tau_{se}^{cls} + \tau_{dev}^{cls}$, is employed in subsequently iterations. Hence, as training progresses, the threshold is incrementally lowered to capture more valuable true positives, benefiting from the enhanced model performance.

IV. EXPERIMENTS

A. Datasets and Evaluation Metrics

We conducted extensive experiments on CoS to assess its effectiveness in real-world and synthetic scenarios across BDD100K [4], SHIFT [32], and ACDC [33] (More details about datasets are in the supplement). Additionally, ablation studies were performed to evaluate the contribution of each module under various configurations of τ_{se}^{cls} , τ_{se}^{loc} in PTC and γ in AIT. All experiments reported mean average precision (mAP) with an evaluation threshold of 0.5.

B. Implementation Details

We adopted FRCNN [34] with pre-trained ResNet-50 as the primary object detector. For the PTC module, initial secure confidence thresholds for classification τ_{se}^{cls} , and localization τ_{se}^{loc} , were set at 0.8 in all experiments, unless otherwise

Fig. 4: Qualitative comparison of CoS with other methods. Images were enhanced for improved visibility. Additional examples are available in the supplement.

specified. Additionally, in AIT, the decay setting γ for τ_{se}^{cls} is $5e-2$, applied post 60% completion of the burn-up stage. During the learning phase, the student network was initiated with a learning rate of $4e-2$. The first 50k iterations form the burn-in stage, focusing on the knowledge transfer from source to target. In the next 50k iterations, the burn-up stage dedicated to the UDA phase, we set the EMA for updating the teacher model at 0.9996. The PLT module is introduced post 40% of the burn-up stage iterations to enhance PLs robustness and capture more potential TPs. All the experiments were conducted on two Nvidia A40 GPUs, with each GPU handling a batch size of nine. The implementation was carried out using the PyTorch framework.

C. Comparison to the state of the art

As shown in Table I, we firstly evaluated CoS against leading state-of-the-art image enhancement [11], [17], [18] and image2image (I2I) translation approaches [18], [19], [28],

[35] on the BDD100K [4]. Owing to the sparse presence of the *train* category in BDD100K, we excluded it from all configurations. Impressively, the proposed CoS demonstrates superior performance, exhibiting approximately a 3.0% increase in AP compared to its rank-1 competitor [11] and nearly a 2.3% improvement over the fully supervised method, especially in small and challenging classes, such as *bicycle*, *rider* and *motorcycle*. Furthermore, Figure 4 show that CoS consistently outperforms in diverse real-world illumination conditions (with and without artificial lighting in low visibility scenarios), whereas other approaches, AT [17] and 2PC [11], either inaccurately detect dark-areas or artificial lighting as false-positives or miss objects (false-negatives) under low illumination (additional results are in the supplement). This underscores the performance improvement of leveraging consistent predictions identified by CoS, no matter how the illumination conditions and the size of objects vary. Additionally, we extracted features from RoI and used t-SNE to visualize them. Figure 3 shows that without CoS, while the model partially aligns the marginal distribution in some classes, it fails to clearly discriminate between categories. However, CoS effectively aligns distributions and discriminates between categories. This confirms the capacity of CoS in transferring knowledge across domains, effectively executing UDA in object detection for nighttime context. Given the limited availability of real-world data, we evaluated CoS on the synthetic dataset SHIFT [32]. Table III (left) indicates that CoS surpasses the oracle model with a 1.5% increase in AP. Furthermore, we evaluate CoS in more challenging situations on ACDC [33], executing UDA solely from daytime images under adverse weather conditions to nighttime contexts. As shown in Table III (right), CoS yields the best results, with improvements of 3.5% and 1.9% over the 2PC [11] and fully supervised model, respectively. This confirms the effectiveness of CoS in both clear and adverse weather conditions, as well as on synthetic data. This stems from target consistency and collaboration between proxy-student and student networks, essential for identifying true positives and extracting valuable latent information.

Methods	$AP_{ST}^{50:95}$	AP_{ST}^{75}	AP_{ST}^{50}	$AP_{AC}^{50:95}$	AP_{AC}^{75}	AP_{AC}^{50}
Oracle	32.0	34.8	49.5	18.1	19.2	37.1
FourierDA [28]	30.3	32.7	47.1	17.0	15.5	34.6
SADAF [31]	30.4	34.6	46.4	16.3	14.0	34.4
AT [17]	29.2	33.0	44.8	16.3	15.6	30.6
2PC [11]	31.9	34.9	49.1	18.7	17.3	36.5
Ours	33.8	37.3	51.0	21.3	20.4	39.0

TABLE III: Quantitative results on SHIFT [32] and ACDC [33] datasets.

D. Ablation Study

To assess the contribution of each module in CoS, we conduct ablation experiments on BDD100K [4] under various setups. As shown in Table II, the initial baseline without proposed modules achieves 35.1% AP. Then, with PTC, model performance improves by 6.2%. Yet, relying solely on consistent targets does not well bridge the large domain gap between

daytime and nighttime contexts. After incorporating the GLT module, CoS achieved 48.4% performance in AP. This indicates that, with the integration of GLT, more valuable latent information extracted from daytime images plays a crucial role in bridging the domain gap. Considering the enhanced model performance across iterations, after introducing the AIT module, CoS reached the best performance on BDD100K with 49.4% AP. This suggests that benefiting from the expanded searching space, CoS is capable of capturing potential TPs that were overlooked by the teacher network and thereby promoting learning progress. With the integration of GLT, PTC, and AIT modulus, CoS effectively narrows the large domain gap, achieving consistent semantic relevance between the daytime and nighttime features.

Fig. 5: Sensitivity analysis on τ_{se}^{cls} and τ_{se}^{loc} .

To further investigate the joint impact of the secure thresholds in classification τ_{se}^{cls} and localization τ_{se}^{loc} , we conducted additional experiments shown in Figure 5. The results demonstrate that the PTC module significantly enhances the proportion of potential True Positives (TPs) as τ_{se}^{loc} increases. However, setting lower thresholds leads to a rapid increase in false positives. Meanwhile, the number of TPs in matched proposals peaks at $\tau_{se}^{loc} = 0.8$. Additionally, setting both τ_{se}^{loc} and τ_{se}^{cls} at 0.8 yields the optimal performance of CoS on the BDD100K [4] dataset.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this study, we introduce CoS, a novel framework designed for UDA in nighttime object detection. CoS incorporates the GLT module to align semantic features between domains, addressing illumination and feature variations. The PTC module, building upon TSN, reliably identifies potential TPs consistently, enhancing generalizability. Complementing this, the AIT module, based on PTC, expands the searching space for potential positive proposals and retains more valuable PLs, ensuring smoother domain adaptation. CoS demonstrates marked improvement in nighttime object detection and outperforms existing methods on benchmark datasets. Future work will aim to bolster CoS robustness in complex and composite conditions across weather, seasons, and cities and integrate with scalable world models to form universal domain detectors, thereby minimizing risks in rare scenarios.

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SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS

In the following pages, we present experimental details, further analysis of the proposed method, and qualitative results.

A. DETAILS OF EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

A.1. Datasets

We evaluate the proposed CoS on three benchmarks for unsupervised domain adaptation (UDA) in nighttime object detection. These benchmarks include real-world and synthetic data, as well as under adverse conditions: Berkeley Deep Drive 100K (BDD100K) [4], SHIFT [32], and Adverse Conditions Dataset with Correspondences (ACDC) [33]. The datasets were divided into training and evaluation sets, adhering to standard settings [11], [17]. BDD100K comprises 100K images across 10 classes. For training, We used 36,728 daytime images and 32,998 nighttime images from 9 classes, excluding the *train* category due to its sparse presence in BDD100K. The nighttime test set includes 4,707 images from these 9 classes. SHIFT includes 19,452 daytime and 8,497 nighttime images across 6 classes for training, with a held-out test set of 1,200 nighttime images. Lastly, on the ACDC dataset, we used 1,200 daytime as the source and 400 nighttime images as the UDA setting. It encompasses 8 classes, representing challenging weather conditions such as fog, snow, and rain. Notably, we do not use any nighttime annotations in the proposed method during training. Overall dataset statistics are summarized in Table IV.

A.2. Implementation Details

We implement the proposed CoS in PyTorch [36] using the Detectron2 [37] framework, with experiments primarily conducted on two Nvidia A40 GPUs. Adhering to standard evaluation settings [11], [17], we conducted controlled experimental setups for equitable comparisons with prior work [5], [18], [19], [30], [31], [38]. We use a ResNet-50 [39] pre-trained on ImageNet [40] as the backbone for both teacher and student networks. In the cooperative students network, a shared RPN was applied, followed by RoI pooling. Different from prior solutions [11], [38], we propose an adaptive dynamic thresholding strategy (AIT) to update τ_{se}^{cls} based on the matched proposals validated by both proxy student and teacher networks. To mitigate the domain divergence between daytime and nighttime contexts, we employ a Global Local Transformation (GLT) module, which includes gamma and contrast transformations at the global level and brightness adjustment in box levels. Additionally, we execute the training on BDD100K [4] and SHIFT [32] from scratch. Due to the limited images and challenging weather conditions in the ACDC [33], we fin-tune the model trained on BDD100K. The code will be released after publication.

B. FURTHER ANALYSIS

B.1. Global-Local-Transformation

In this part, we detail the GLT module setup presented in Section III-B. Our objective is to facilitate UDA in transitioning from daytime to nighttime object detection without using

annotations in the target domain. To achieve it, we first employ a parameter-free GLT module, leveraging prior knowledge from the target domain, to transform daytime images into nighttime contexts and minimize domain divergence. Specifically, we incorporate seven distinct input transformations of four types, none of which demands learned parameters: additive noises (Gaussian noise), visibility correction (brightness, contrast, and gamma adjustment), image quality degradation (Gaussian blur), and contrastive features (randomKeep and local brightness transformation at box-level). Figure 6 illustrates the pipeline of GLT by step-by-step transformation using one source example and its final outcome. Leveraging the prior knowledge from the target domain, we diminish the visibility and quality of images in the source domain to simulate characteristics of images captured during low-illumination conditions. Meanwhile, we introduce contrastive features at the box level to assist the model in identifying semantic relevance across different domains, thereby boosting its performance. Figure 7 demonstrates more examples of the final transformed results. In this way, we construct the daytime to (augmented) nighttime image pairs, serving as an intermediary domain. These image pairs, combined with source domain annotations, guide the learning of the student network and achieve a smooth transition in UDA adapted to real nighttime imagery. In the following, the detailed settings of each type of corruption are listed:

- **Gaussian blur:** We randomly apply Gaussian blur to images with a probability of 0.5. The Gaussian kernel size is set to 11 with a random sigma s that varies between 0.1 and 2.0.
- **Gmma Correction:** We employ gamma correction to images with a probability of 0.4. The value dynamically varies for each image between 1.25 and 5.
- **RandomKeep:** A randomly selected region of an enhanced source image is replaced with the corresponding area from the previous step.
- **Brightness Adjustment:** To simulate the transition from daytime to nighttime scenarios, we adjust brightness with a probability of 0.55. It is channel-specific and determined by the channel-wise differences in μ_c between daytime and nighttime images. The adjustment parameter is calculated as the product of the luminance offset and a random factor β , uniformly sampled between 0.2 and 0.8.
- **Contrast Adjustment:** We randomly apply contrast adjustment to images with a probability of 0.55. The contrast offset is the ratio of channel-wise σ between nighttime and daytime images. To simulate the contrast variability in diverse scenarios, the contrast parameter is then determined by multiplying this offset by a random factor, uniformly sampled between 0.2 and 0.8.
- **Gaussian Noise:** We add Gaussian Noise to images with a probability of 0.5, following a normal distribution $\mathcal{N}(0, 0.1)$. Pixel values are adjusted to remain within the 0 to 1 range after adding noise.

Dataset	URL	Num of Classes	Num. of Images		
			Daytime	Nighttime (UDA)	Nighttime (Eval)
BDD100K [4]	Link	10	36,728	32,998	4,707
SHIFT [41]	Link	6	19,452	8,497	1,200
ACDC [33]	Link	8	12,00	400	400

TABLE IV: Dataset statistics.

Fig. 6: Examples of input transformation utilized in experiments. From left top to right bottom, we visualize the original image followed by the results of seven transformation types. These include additive noises (Gaussian Noise), visibility correction (brightness, contrast, and gamma adjustment), image quality degradation (Gaussian blur), and contrastive features (randomKeep and local transformation).

- **Local Transformation:** This transformation focuses on introducing localized low-light conditions and contrastive features at the box level. Similar to global transformation, a random low-light adjustment parameter ranging from 1.5 to 5.0 is applied selectively to specific regions (randomly set a pixel coordinate inside bounding boxes as the center point and position a mask either horizontally or vertically). It serves to simulate the complex luminance variations typical in nighttime environments.

B.2. Proxy-based Target Consistent Mechanism

In Section III-C of the manuscript, we elaborate on the PTC module, which aims to achieve consistent targets between teacher and proxy-student networks. Its detailed pipeline is outlined in Algorithm 1. Initially, the teacher network’s outputs $\mathcal{O}^T(\hat{\mathcal{B}}^T, \hat{\mathcal{C}}^T)$ are filtered using a static threshold, as in traditional methods [11], [30], to produce preliminary pseudo labels. To address overlooked samples, we merge filtered outputs (with classification confidences below τ_{lp}^{cls} and not exceeding τ_{se}^{cls}) with outputs from the proxy student network. If they share identical categorical predictions and high localization consistency ($\text{argmax}(\hat{\mathcal{C}}_i^T) = \text{argmax}(\hat{\mathcal{C}}_i^P)$ and $\text{IoU}(\hat{\mathcal{B}}_i^P, \hat{\mathcal{B}}_i^T) > \tau_{se}^{loc}$), these outputs from the teacher network will be used as extended pseudo-label candidates. Subsequently, both initial and extended pseudo labels are utilized during the UDA phase to guide the learning of the student network. Additional examples of mined proposals for potentially overlooked objects can be found in Figure 8.

Algorithm 1 ProxyTargetConsistency

Input: Outputs from Teacher and Proxy Student: $\mathcal{O}^T(\hat{\mathcal{B}}^T, \hat{\mathcal{C}}^T)$, $\mathcal{O}^P(\hat{\mathcal{B}}^P, \hat{\mathcal{C}}^P)$; Upper and lower bound thresholds based on classification confidence: τ_{se}^{cls} , τ_{lb}^{cls} ; Threshold for validating matched proposals: τ_{se}^{loc} .

- 1: Initialize valid map vm .
- 2: **for** \mathcal{O}_i^T in \mathcal{O}^T **do**
- 3: $dxT = \text{argmax}(\hat{\mathcal{C}}_i^T)$
- 4: **if** $\hat{\mathcal{C}}_i^T[dxT] \geq \tau_{se}^{cls}$ **then** ▷ traditional cls_based
- 5: $vm[i] = \text{True}$ ▷ as Eqn. 5
- 6: **else if** $\hat{\mathcal{C}}_i^T[dxT] > \tau_{lb}^{cls}$ **then** ▷ check overlooked
- 7: **for** \mathcal{O}_i^P in \mathcal{O}^P **do**
- 8: $dxP = \text{argmax}(\hat{\mathcal{C}}_i^P)$
- 9: $iou = \text{IoU}(\hat{\mathcal{B}}_{i_{dxP}}^P, \hat{\mathcal{B}}_{i_{dxT}}^T)$ ▷ loc_consistency
- 10: **if** $dxP == dxT$ and $iou \geq \tau_{se}^{loc}$ **then**
- 11: $vm[i] = \text{True}$ ▷ Eqn. 6
- 12: **end if**
- 13: **end for**
- 14: **end if**
- 15: **end for**
- 16: **return** $\mathcal{O}^T[vm]$ ▷ target_consistency

These examples demonstrate the ability of CoS to identify not only potential true positives but also real, previously unannotated objects in the ground truth. Furthermore, we noted that the PTC module is more capable of mining the overlooked

Fig. 7: Examples of enhanced daytime images by the GLT module (rows 1 and 3 depict raw daytime images; rows 2 and 4 show enhanced daytime images, incorporating priors from nighttime scenarios). Best viewed when zoomed in.

small, challenging objects through localization consistency. This indicates that our approach enables the network to extract consistent semantic relevance among objects in images.

B.3. Adaptive IoU-informed Thresholding

In this section, we present ablation studies conducted on the γ parameter in the AIT module on the BDD100K and SHIFT datasets. Similar to τ_{se}^{cls} and τ_{se}^{loc} , the decay parameter γ can also impact the model’s ability to capture potential true positives across iterations. Specifically, a high γ can result in too many false negatives, while a low value may increase false positives, compromising model performance. Building upon the PTC module, we develop an IoU-informed dynamic thresholding strategy for adjusting γ dynamically. Figure V showcases the AIT module achieves superior performances over the baseline. The optimal performance in AP is achieved at $\gamma = 0.05$, with a performance improvement of 1% and 1.3% in AP on BDD100K [4] and SHIFT [32] datasets, respectively. However, increasing γ to 0.07 leads to a performance drop of around 0.3% on BDD100K and 1.1% on SHIFT, compared to the results at $\gamma = 0.05$. This suggests that a rapid reduction in τ_{se}^{cls} leads to an increase in false positives within pseudo-labels due to the limited learning capacity of the student network.

γ	AP_{BDD}	AP_{BDD}^L	AP_{BDD}^M	AP_{BDD}^S	AP_{ST}	AP_{ST}^L	AP_{ST}^M	AP_{ST}^S
w/o	48.4	44.8	27.2	9.6	49.7	76.1	57.6	12.1
0.03	49.0	46.8	27.5	9.9	50.4	79.3	59.5	12.0
0.05	49.4	45.9	27.9	10.2	51.0	78.9	60.1	12.3
0.07	48.7	45.9	27.4	9.6	49.9	77.8	57.1	11.5

TABLE V: Sensitivity analysis of γ on BDD100K (BDD) [4] and SHIFT (ST) [32].

C. QUALITATIVE RESULTS

In this section, we present the qualitative results of CoS on the BDD100K [4] and SHIFT [32] datasets. We contrast our results with three other strong models, AT [17], SADA [31], and 2PC [11]. As shown in Figure 9, the color-coded bounding boxes signify the class of detected instances in relation to the ground truth. It is observed that most models perform effectively in conditions of well-fit artificial lighting. However, 2PC [11] often incorrectly identifies more false positives, notably for non-existent objects, while the adaptive teacher model has difficulty in glass reflecting due to the artificial lighting. Differently, CoS demonstrates consistent performance in localizing and identifying objects in the nighttime context, regardless of the intensity of artificial light sources. Additionally, CoS often yields dense predictions for small, distant objects from the camera. As highlighted in DPL [13], positive dense pseudo labels potentially retain richer information. This suggests a reason why our model surpasses the baseline and other UDA models in performance. On the SHIFT dataset [32], as demonstrated in Figure 10, SADA [31] and 2PC [11] struggle to identify objects in very-low light scenarios. In contrast, CoS exhibits superior performance under diverse illumination conditions. This further underscores the effectiveness of CoS in UDA for nighttime object detection.

Fig. 8: Examples of matched proposals between the teacher and proxy-student network on BDD100K [4]. Uncertain proposals ($\hat{C}_i^T < \tau_{se}^{cls}$) from the teacher are outlined in red dashed boxes; those proposals from the proxy student appear in green dotted boxes. Ground truths for matched true positives are highlighted in blue filled boxes. Best viewed when zoomed in.

Fig. 9: Qualitative results for the BDD100K [4] dataset are displayed from left to right, showcasing the raw image, followed by results from Adaptive Teacher (AT) [17], 2PCNet (2PC) [11], and the proposed, with the ground truth presented on the far right.

Fig. 10: Qualitative results for the SHIFT [32] dataset are displayed from left to right, showcasing the raw image, followed by results from Scale-Aware Domain Adaptive FRCNN (SADA) [31], 2PCNet (2PC) [11], and the proposed CoS, with the ground truth presented on the far right.